

Net Zero Digital Research Infrastructure Scoping Project

Announcement of Opportunity: invitation to submit a proposal

Call issued on: 29th March 2022

Dates of Sandpit: there will be two events:

A: 9th and 11th May

B: 23rd and 25th May

Venue: Online

Full Proposals deadline: 4pm on 13th June, 2022

Funding available: up to £710k (80% FEC)

Funded projects start date: July 2022

How to apply: <https://ukri-net-zero-sandpit.eventbrite.co.uk/>

Assessment process: Projects will present ideas to an expert panel at the end of the Sandpit. A number will be invited to submit full proposals. The submitted proposal be assessed by the panel of mentors.

Timetable:

Activity	Deadline
Deadline for application to join sandpit	4pm 25 th April
Invitations to join	29th April
Sandpit A	10am-1pm, 9th and 11th May
Sandpit B	10am-1pm, 23rd and 25th May
Deadline for submission of outline proposals	12th and 26th May, 4pm
Validation panel meets	13th and 27th May
Deadline for submission of fully costed proposals	June 13th, 4pm
Latest start date for projects	September 2022

1. Summary

As part of a suite of activities UKRI invites researchers and practitioners to come together in two 'sandpit' style workshops.

The aim is for participants to network and leverage their experience and expertise to design collaborative proof-of-concept studies and community engagement workshops. Evidence gathered from the studies and workshops will be used to inform recommendations and map a pathway for the implementation of the UKRI Net Zero strategic ambitions within the Digital Research Infrastructure.

Funding of £500k (80% FEC) will be available for up to 5 proof-of-concept studies, and £210 (80% FEC) for up to 8 community engagement workshops. This event is managed by the Centre for Environmental Data Analysis (CEDA) on behalf of UKRI as part of the UKRI Net Zero Digital Research Infrastructure Scoping project introduced below¹.

Each Sandpit will take place over two 3-hour sessions and participants must be there for the whole duration, participating in all activities. Applicants will collaboratively develop ideas for proposals during the Sandpit and submit outline proposals for the consideration of a panel of experts. Those invited to submit full proposals will be required to finalise the applications within a few weeks of the sandpit.

2. Background

The UKRI Net Zero Digital Research Infrastructure Scoping Project will:

- Collect evidence to inform UKRI Digital Research Infrastructure Investment decisions.
- Provide as recommendations for UKRI and their community with an outline roadmap for achieving carbon neutrality in their Digital Research Infrastructure by 2040 or sooner.
- Enable UKRI to play a positive and leading role in the national and global transition to a sustainable economy.

The infrastructure elements in scope include all the UKRI owned and majority funded digital research infrastructure. The role of connected devices will also be considered, both in the context of the carbon footprint that users need to incur to connect to the infrastructure and as an indication of the direction and speed of technological change.

In addition to the roles of operator, procurer and service provider alluded to above, UKRI and their research community have a critical role as influencers and innovators. As a customer for computer hardware UKRI has a tiny leverage in the global market, but the influence of UKRI science on national and global attitudes to sustainability in general, and the net zero target in particular, is immense.

This project does not aim to place limits on researchers, but to develop a framework which can enhance the contribution that the community makes to a huge societal challenge. Just as national infrastructure investments are considered in the context of expected return on investment, we will consider the expected benefits of resources, including potentially limited power and offsetting capacity, allocated to digital research infrastructure.

A substantial component of the current carbon footprint of the digital research infrastructure is electricity. We will explore measures to reduce electricity usage as well as measures aimed at procuring electricity with a low or zero carbon footprint. The manufacture of hardware also has a substantial footprint, and for laptops and phones this is the dominant component of the footprint. For well-run data centres, on the other hand, the electricity use tends to dominate,

¹ net-zero-dri.ceda.ac.uk

but the footprint of manufacturing, which includes both electricity to drive factories and emissions of volatiles released in integrated circuit manufacture remains to be addressed.

Measures to extract carbon dioxide from the atmosphere will also be considered, as a means to balancing any unavoided emissions.

With the role of UKRI as an influencer in mind, all aspects of the project will be considered from a broad perspective, and acknowledge the risk that policy intended to reduce emissions can often simply displace them.

We will look at the part that changes in behaviour can play in delivering net zero emissions, and at the experience in other areas of delivering change in the research culture to adapt to societal objectives and expectations.

The net zero target clearly raises transdisciplinary, transgenerational and transnational issues. We seek to be informed by similar initiatives and practitioners from across the globe and to encourage participation from young people in the early stages of their careers.

The evidence collected will take various forms, including direct quantitative evidence collected from current facilities, an extensive literature review, community workshops, proof-of-concept studies and other forms of expert consultation.

The UK is embarking transition to a sustainable economy with a target for net-zero carbon emissions. The evolving nature of the net-zero challenge for digital technology and lack of cohesion in the research and user community is limiting both research and innovation developments and policy benefits. Consequently, stakeholders are faced with multiple evidence streams leading to inconsistent analysis and inefficient application of new science to support policy and action. To address these challenges the programme will support a range of proof-of-concept studies and workshops.

The ambitions of the UKRI Net Zero DRI Roadmap Scoping Project are to:

- Collect evidence to inform UKRI Digital Research Infrastructure Investment decisions
- Provide UKRI and their community with an outline roadmap for achieving carbon neutrality in their Digital Research Infrastructure by 2040 or sooner
- Enable UKRI to play a positive and leading role in the national and global transition to a sustainable economy

3. Scope of the Opportunity

3.1. Proof of Concept Studies and Workshops

This opportunity offers both funds for proof-of-concept studies demonstrating practical steps towards a net zero DRI and for the hosting of workshops to promote discussion and gather knowledge on relevant research. Both categories of projects will be considered in parallel to allow cross-fertilisation of ideas.

Further details on web site:

- <https://net-zero-dri.ceda.ac.uk/proof-of-concept/>
- <https://net-zero-dri.ceda.ac.uk/workshops/>

4. The 'Sandpit' events

4.1. What is a Sandpit?

A Sandpit is an intensive, interactive workshop designed to produce highly innovative proposals. Participants come together in a creative, free-thinking environment and immerse themselves deeply in a collaborative process around an important challenge.

The nature of the Sandpit requires the development of a high degree of trust between participants in order to make the required breakthroughs in thinking. The goal is to bring individuals together to interact and engage in free thinking on first principles, to learn from one another and create an integrated vision for projects and workshops. While the sharing of these ideas is strongly encouraged within the Sandpit, participants are asked to respect confidentiality outside of the Sandpit.

4.2. What will happen at the Sandpit?

The Sandpit is a facilitated workshop designed to encourage creative thinking and new collaborations. This is a relatively short event and will therefore be quite intensive.

The Sandpit will include opportunities or activities that allow participants to:

- Get to know everyone in the room
- Work towards a common understanding of language and terminology
- Share understanding, and defining the scope of the issue
- Generate ideas by taking part in breakout sessions focused on the problem domain
- Give and receive peer feedback on the ideas
- Form groups and subsequently develop proof-of-concept studies and workshops.
- Draft summary proposals for potential studies and workshops.

The full agenda for the Sandpit will be provided in a separate document.

4.3. Dates and Themes of the Sandpits.

The sandpit events are for allocating funds to both the proof-of-concept studies and community engagement workshops.

There will be two sandpit events, Sandpit A from 10am-1pm on the 9th and 11th of May, and Sandpit B from 10am-1pm on the 23rd and 25th May. The sandpits will be online activities, taking place on zoom, and participants will be expected to attend both days of the sandpit.

Sandpit A will focus on **community and organisational challenges** such as: user facing services, data management, behaviour change, training, proportionality of energy use, who are the winners/losers, and monitoring and driving change.

Sandpit B will focus on **technical and operational challenges** such as: hardware procurement, design and architecture of infrastructure, cloud platforms, consolidation, power management and efficiency, end-of-life, and carbon capture and offsetting.

4.4. Objectives of the Sandpit

The objective of this sandpit is to network and leverage the experience and expertise of the participants to design collaborative proof-of-concept studies and community engagement workshops. Evidence gathered from the studies and workshops will be used

to inform recommendations and map a pathway for the implementation of the UKRI Net Zero strategic ambitions within the Digital Research Infrastructure.

5. Programme requirements

5.1. Implementation and delivery

Projects must be delivered between July 2022 and December 2022. Exact funding profiles and timings will be agreed with successful projects before award.

5.2. Project Outputs

All projects funded through these events must have a clear plan to contribute evidence and recommendations for inclusion in the Net Zero DRI Roadmap Scoping project final report. Evidence should be presented in the form of Key Finding, and each Key Finding should contain a description of the finding, a presentation of supporting evidence, and a reasoned estimate of the degree of confidence in the Key Finding. Further guidelines on the presentation of Key Findings will be presented at the sandpit events.

5.3. NERC Facilities

Prior to submitting a proposal, applicants wishing to use a UKRI service or facility must contact the facility to seek agreement that they could provide the service required. Applicants wishing to use most UKRI facilities will need to submit a mandatory 'technical assessment' with their proposal.

5.4. Programme management

As part of the overall Net Zero DRI Scoping project, successful projects are expected as a condition of award to participate and collaborate with cross-cutting and integrating activities - in particular through participation in a joint workshop to present results and contributing to a literature review.

5.5. Reporting requirements

As with all UKRI grant holders, there will be a requirement to report through the UKRI reporting system; this is required annually and continues for up to five years post grant end. Further details on reporting will be provided at the sandpit events.

6. Application process

6.1. Who can attend the Sandpits?

The sandpits are open to researchers who are qualified to hold UKRI research grants and their associates and collaborators.

Final proposals should be led by someone eligible for UKRI grants. Other researchers and practitioners may attend and seek to contribute as partners.

The final participant list will be confirmed by the funders to ensure a balance of diversity across institutions and research areas, and participants will be notified by CEDA.

6.2 Applying to attend the Sandpits

To apply to attend the sandpits fill out the [online application form](#) and provide a brief summary (up to 200 words) of your initial idea. The summary should describe the project or workshop concept and how it is expected to contribute to achieving a net-zero DRI by 2040 or sooner. Applications must be submitted before 4pm on April 25th. We will review applications and

invite successful applicants to the sandpits on April 29th.

6.3 At the Sandpits

Projects will be developed during the Sandpits. On the day following the end of the sandpit participants will submit a written summary of the proposed projects on the provided template (see Annex 1) to an expert panel comprised of the mentors and funder representatives.

6.4. Full Proposals

Details of the process for full proposals will be made available before the sandpit event.

7. Assessment Process

Outline proposals will undergo 'real time' peer review in the week of the Sandpit. This will be based on the submitted outline template (Annex 1) and a presentation given to the panel. The panel will be comprised of the sandpit Director and mentors with representatives of the funders as observers. The panel will recommend a number of proposals for funding and to submit full proposals via JeS and provide written feedback on each proposal. The panel will reconvene following submission of full proposals to re-review and validate their decisions regarding proposals to support.

Proposals for proof-of-concept studies will be assessed on the following criteria:

- Excellence: is the proposed work breaking new ground and changing the way in which we view energy efficiency within the DRI,
- Evidence: will the proposed work produce authoritative evidence that can be used to underpin recommendations for the UKRI Net Zero DRI roadmap? Studies will be asked to propose recommendations backed by their evidence.
- Effectiveness: is there a clear plan of work? Have the proposal team thought through the process well enough to deliver the project?

Similar criteria will be used for assessing workshop proposals:

- Excellence: does the proposed approach have a clear plan for creating and running events which will convey the latest published research and operational thinking on each topic?
- Evidence: will the proposed event(s) produce authoritative evidence and recommendations that can be used to underpin recommendations for the UKRI Net Zero DRI roadmap?
- Effectiveness: is there a clear plan for the event(s)? Have the proposal team thought through the process well enough? Is there creative use of online meeting and discussion options?

Feedback will be provided to both successful and unsuccessful applicants.

The funders will use the recommendations of the panel along with the overall call requirements and the available budget in making the final funding decisions.

8. Contact

Please contact support@ceda.ac.uk and put "Net Zero Sandpit" in the subject line.

Annex 1 – Project Summary Template for submission at end of Sandpit

A1.1 Outline Proposal: Net Zero DRI Scoping Sandpit

Mentor at Sandpit

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Event Attended : A or B (delete as appropriate)

Project title

[up to 150 characters]

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Activities

Please **X** in the WP being addressed by this proposal:

Workshop	
Proof-of-concept Study	

Proposed duration

(proposals must start between July and September 2022 and end by end of December 2022)

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Applicants

Role	Name	Organisation	Division or Department

Additional applicants not present at the sandpit event

Please provide names and justification for the inclusion of any additional co-investigators from your institution who are not present at this sandpit event, who you wish to be included in your project team. Please also reference any skills gaps you wish to fill [up to 200 words].

The Problem to be Addressed

State briefly the specific challenge that your project will address. [up to 300 words].

Summary and objectives

[up to 300 words].

How will the project achieve its aims?

Provide a summary of the research to be carried out and the methods to be employed [up to 300 words]

Total Budget

Please provide an estimate of the total budget at 80% FEC:

A1.2 Proposal Finalisation

Further details to be completed after acceptance by panel, by June 13th.

Data Management Plan

Provide a summary of the data which will be generated by the project (including tables and data for figures) and plans to archive the data [up to 150 words]. For environmental data the [NERC Data Policy](#) must be adhered to.

Project team

Please provide a short statement on the specific roles and contribution to the project of each named investigator, and detail on how you will work as a team, including reference to project management and communication plans between the team as necessary [up to 300 words]

Social and economic impact

Please describe the potential wider range of impacts that could be generated from the proposed research [up to 300 words]

Staffing required

Please list the number of postdocs, research assistants and technicians required for the project [up to 200 words]

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Budget

Please provide a rough estimate of the full costs of the research proposed (including all estates and indirect costs etc) and the indicative breakdown between partners

FULL PROJECT COSTS	100% FEC £	80% FEC £
Directly Incurred staff		
Directly Incurred T&S		
Directly Incurred Other		
Directly Allocated Investigators		
Directly Allocated Estates		
Directly Allocated Other		
Indirect		
TOTAL COSTS		

Breakdown by partner:

Institution	100% FEC	80% FEC
<i>(Institution 1)</i>		
<i>(Institution 2)</i>		
<i>(Institution 3)</i>		

[Please add additional lines as needed]

Are there any ethical implications arising from the proposed research?

[YES/NO]

If the answer is yes, please provide brief details of what they are and how they would be addressed.

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All personal data submitted on this form will be processed in accordance with UK data protection legislation as set out in the [UKRI Privacy Notice](#). NERC will record your information for the purpose of assessing, processing, and contacting you regarding your application. For the purposes of assessing and processing your application your details provided in this form and on any presentation will also be shared with the other funding partners (MRC, ESRC, EPSRC) and an expert panel of reviewers. Submission of this application provides your consent to the sharing of the data with the parties described above. MRC, ESRC and EPSRC will not retain your personal details beyond the period required for the purposes of assessing and processing. We will not pass your information on to any other third party without obtaining your prior permission.